

IN-SITU OBSERVATION OF STRAIN FIELD IN ADHESIVELY BONDED CFRP JOINTS UNDER MODE I AND MODE II LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Microscopic failure mechanisms in adhesively bonded carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) joints under mode I and mode II loading were discussed in the study. In-situ observation with an optical microscope was conducted in order to observe the microscopic damage in adhesive layers. The microscopic damage in adhesive layers was quantitatively evaluate by using the digital image correlation (DIC) method. Strain concentration along CFRP/adhesive interface was observed under mode I loading. This result implies that interfacial damage zone was formed in the adhesive layer. On the other hand, strain concentration and microcracks around polyester carriers embedded in the adhesive was observed under mode II loading. Macroscopic crack growth occurred due to the coalescing of microcracks under mode II loading. The maximum principal strain in the adhesive layer under mode II loading at the onset of crack growth was significantly larger than that under mode I loading. In order to simulate the microscopic failure in the adhesive layers, damage analyses using finite element method (FEM) were carried out. Adhesive resin, CFRPs, and polyester carrier were modeled for the analyses. The Drucker-Prager yielding condition and simple damage model were employed. Interfacial damage zone was not able to be simulated by the present method because thermal stress and constrain in the width direction were not considered in the damage analysis. Contrary to the damage analysis under mode I loading, morphology of fracture, strain distribution, and location of strain concentration were successfully simulated under mode II loading by using the present method.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates in aerospace structures is on the rise due to their lightweight and excellent specific strength. Although mechanical fasteners are most commonly used for joining of aircraft structures, adhesively bonded joints provide further advantages (e.g. reduction in weight and manufacturing cost), whereas the failure mechanism of adhesively bonded joints are not fully characterized. Thus, further understanding of the failure mechanisms in CFRP adhesively bonded joints are required to improve the airworthiness.

Failure mechanisms of ductile adhesives involve complex deformation, because the process and plastic zone in the thin adhesive layer is large [1]. Several researchers conducted in-situ observation in microscale in order to clarify the damage mechanisms under mode I and mode II loading [2-7]. The previous works qualitatively observed microscopic damage processes in adhesive layers, but quantitative evaluation in adhesive layers is also very important to further understand failure mechanisms and compare with numerical simulation results.

On the other hand, damage analyses of adhesively bonded joints using finite element method (FEM) with the cohesive zone model (CZM) is widely applied because the CZM can easily simulate the nonlinear behavior of adhesives [8]. However, the crack propagation path must be defined in advance by using the CZM for damage analyses. Thus, simulation of crack kinking as well as interfacial failure is difficult using the CZM.

Against these backdrops, this study was performed to quantitatively evaluate microscopic damage mechanisms in adhesively bonded CFRP joints. High-magnification in-situ observation of fracture toughness tests was conducted under both mode I and mode II loading with an optical microscope. In addition, damage analyses using the Drucker-Prager yielding condition and simple linear damage model were carried out in order to simulate microscopic failure in the adhesive layer.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Data reduction scheme

Figure 1 shows a schematic drawing of a wedge loaded double cantilever (DCB) specimen used for the mode I fracture toughness tests. One end of the specimen is fixed, while the other end is split apart by a pair of wedges. Hence, the wedge loaded DCB specimen is suitable for stationary observation compared with the standard DCB specimen [9].

Mode I energy release rate, G_I , for the wedge loaded DCB specimen is given by [10]:

$$G_I = \frac{3P_y\delta[(a + \Delta) + d\psi]^2}{b(a + \Delta)^2[2(a + \Delta) + 3d\psi]} \quad (1)$$

where, P_y is the opening load, δ is the opening displacement, a is crack length, Δ is correction factor of crack length [11], d is the distance between the neutral axis and point of application as shown in Figure 1(b), $\psi (=P_x/P_y)$ is the ratio of axial load, P_x , to opening load, P_y , b is the width of the specimen. The correction factor, Δ , was calculated by the iterative calculation based on Ref. [10] method. Likewise, crack length is estimated by apparent compliance $C_{app} (= \delta/P_y)$ by assuming linear relationship between cube root of C_{app} and crack length, a based on Ref. [10] method.

Figure 2 shows a schematic drawing of a doubly end notched tension (DENT) specimen [12] used for mode II fracture toughness tests. Pure mode II loading can be achieved by applying only a tensile load. Since bending deformation does not occurred, the DENT specimen is suitable for in-situ observation compared with the standard mode II specimens.

mode II energy release rate, G_{II} , for the DENT specimen is given by:

$$G_{II} = \frac{h_2 P \delta}{4b(h_2 a + 2h_1 L)} \quad (2)$$

where h_1 and h_2 are thickness of outer and middle adherends, respectively, P is the applied load, δ is the displacement of specimen, b is width of the specimen, a is crack length, and L is gauge length of the

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of a wedge loaded double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing of a doubly end notched tension (DENT) specimen.

specimen as shown in Figure 2. Crack length, a , during fracture toughness tests is estimated by compliance, $C (= \delta/P)$ as well as the standard ENF tests [13].

2.2 Material and specimen

Unidirectional CFRP laminates (T800S/2592, Toray) were used for the adherends. The volume fraction of fiber and nominal thickness of a layer were approximately 65% [14] and 0.14 mm, respectively. The CFRP prepreg was cured at 135°C for 90 minutes in an autoclave. Nylon peel plies (51789-060, Precision Fabric Group) were used for the surface treatment of the laminates. These laminates were bonded with modified epoxy structural adhesive films (NB102, Mitsubishi Chemical Carbon Fiber and Composites) at 120°C for 90 minutes in an autoclave. The adhesive film is supported by non-woven polyester carriers. The initial delamination of the specimen was introduced by inserting FEP film (25 μm in thickness).

Two laminates were bonded to fabricate the wedge loaded DCB specimens. The stacking sequence of the laminates was $[0^\circ]_{16}$. Thickness of the adherends, h , was approximately 2.2 mm. The bonded laminates were cut into strip shape. The width, b , and length, L , of the specimen were 20 mm and 150 mm, respectively. The length of the initial delamination, a_0 , was set to 60 mm. Average adhesive thickness of the specimen was 0.14 mm.

Three laminates were bonded to fabricate the DENT specimens. The stacking sequence of outer and middle substrates were $[0^\circ]_8$ and $[0^\circ]_{24}$, respectively. The thickness of the outer substrates, h_1 , and middle substrates, h_2 , were approximately 1.1 mm and 3.4 mm, respectively. The bonded laminates were cut into strip shape. The width, b , and length of the specimen were 20 mm and 390 mm. The gauge length, L , was 220 mm. The length of the initial delamination, a_0 , was approximately 35 mm. Average adhesive thickness of the specimen was 0.22 mm. GFRP tabs (70 mm in length, 1.5 mm in thickness) were bonded to the specimen. Thus, distance between the tabs was 250 mm.

2.3 In-situ observation

Figures 3 and 4 display the experimental setup of the in-situ observation under mode I and mode II loading, respectively. A monochrome industrial camera (DMK33UP1300, The Imaging Source) and 0.75-5 \times optical microscope (MV-550, WRAYMER) with a 2 \times objective lens were used. The resolution of the digital image was 1280 \times 960 pixels. The optical microscope was set on a stage and vibration isolator. Field of view (FOV) of each photograph was 1.0 \times 0.8 mm i.e. the spatial resolution was 0.8 pixels/ μm . Observation over a large region was carried out for mode II testing by moving the stage along the adhesive layer [15] because plastic and damage zone is widely developed under mode II loading. The final FOV were 0.8 \times 1.0 mm for mode I testing, 0.8 \times 3.0 mm for mode II testing. One of the two cracks was observed for mode II testing. Surface roughness of the specimen was utilized as the speckle pattern for the DIC analysis. The specimens were illuminated by oblique light emitting diode (LED) lights in order to enhance the contrast. Two-dimensional strain field was obtained with a commercial DIC package (DaVis 8.2.2, LaVision). The reference images were updated for each step because large deformation occurred in the adhesive layer. Strain components were calculated relative to the first image. Subset size of the DIC analyses was 24 \times 24 pixels for all analyses. This value is equivalent to 19.2 \times 19.2 μm . The subsets overlapped by 50% in both x and y directions.

2.4 Experimental procedure

The mode I tests were carried out at a constant crosshead speed of 8.3×10^{-6} m/s (0.5 mm/min.)

using a universal tester (AG-50kNXDplus, Shimadzu). Figure 3 exhibits the experimental setup of the wedge loaded DCB tests. A pair of wedges (90° in wedge angle) was attached to the load cell to split the specimen apart, hence, giving the load ratio, ψ , a value of 1. Opening load, P_y , and opening displacement, δ , were determined by the load output of load cell and crosshead displacement. The tests were temporally suspended during the photographing process at an interval of 0.25 mm in crosshead displacement.

The mode II tests were carried out at a constant crosshead speed of 8.3×10^{-6} m/s (0.5 mm/min.) using a universal tester (AG-250kNXplus, Shimadzu). Figure 4 shows the experimental setup of the DENT tests. Two clip-on extensometers (DTC-A-5, Kyowa Electric Instruments) were attached to measure the elongation of the specimen. CFRP extenders gave the gauge length, L , as 220 mm. The tests were temporally suspended during the photographing process at an interval of 0.1 or 0.2 mm in extensometer displacement.

2.5 Experimental results and discussion

Figures 5(a) and (b) depict the maximum principal strain, ϵ_1 , distribution contour obtained by the mode I fracture toughness tests and DIC method. The adhesive/CFRP interfaces are indicated by white dotted lines. Strain bands were observed from the crack tip to the CFRP/adhesive interfaces. Crack propagated along CFRP/adhesive interface. These results imply that the interface damage zones were formed due to the constraint by the adherends as reported in Ref [7]. ϵ_1 at the onset of interfacial crack growth was approximately 30%.

Figures 6(a)-(c) show the maximum principal strain, ϵ_1 , distribution contour obtained by the mode II fracture toughness tests and DIC method. The observed region was 0.9-1.6 mm from the crack tip. The adhesive/CFRP interfaces are indicated by white dotted lines. Strain bands were observed along carrier/resin interface. Strain concentration was observed between polyester fibers as mode II energy release rate, G_{II} , increased. However, strain concentration along CFRP/adhesive interface was not observed for the mode II tests. Although the observation area is 0.9-1.6 mm away from the crack tip, microcracks appeared between polyester fibers when the maximum principal strain, ϵ_1 , reached approximately 70%. ϵ_1 in the resin partially exceeded 100% before macroscopic crack growth without visible breakage.

Figure 3: Experimental setup of wedge loaded DCB test.

Figure 4: Experimental setup of DENT test.

Figure 5: Maximum principal strain distribution under mode I loading around crack tip.

Figure 6: Maximum principal strain distribution under mode II loading (0.9-1.6 mm from crack tip).

3 FINITE-ELEMENT ANALYSIS

3.1 Finite element model and analytical procedure

Microscopic failure process was simulated by using FEM. Adhesive resin, CFRP adherends, and polyester carriers were modeled for the analyses. Two kinds of model were prepared. One is an analytical model around a crack tip under mode I loading (henceforth, mode I model). The other one is that without crack failed by mode II (shear) loading (henceforth, mode II model). These two models correspond to experimental results shown in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. Figures 7 and 8 shows the analysis model and the boundary conditions for the mode I and mode II models. 8-node solid elements were used for the modeling. The dimensions of the analysis model are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. The carriers were placed at the same position as the observed with an optical microscope. The carrier fibers were randomly oriented in the adhesive film used for the experiment, but two-dimensional distribution was assumed in order to simplify the models. The diameter of the carrier fiber was $15 \mu\text{m}$. The models consist of 1 element in z -direction. The number of nodes and elements are 128482 and 63659 for the mode I model, and 91152 and 45175 for the mode II model. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in the longitudinal direction of the adhesive layer for the mode II model. One of the two side in z -

direction is fixed and the other side is not fixed. The CFRP parts were modeled as orthotropic elastic bodies. Mechanical properties of T800S/2592 laminates are shown in Table 1. The adhesive part was modeled as an elastic-plastic body. the mechanical properties of NB102 adhesive obtained by tensile and shear tests is shown in Table 2. The Drucker-Prager yielding condition was employed in order to consider hydrostatic stress dependence on the yielding condition. Associated flow rule was employed for the hardening law. Equivalent plastic strain was used as the ductile failure criterion of the adhesive. The onset of the damage as a function of stress triaxiality is shown in Table 3. Linear evolution of the damage variable was assumed with increasing effective plastic displacement. The fracture energy, G_f , was set to 0.25 kJ/m². The carriers were modeled as elastic perfectly plastic bodies. Young's modulus, Poisson's ration, and yield stress of the carrier were $E = 3000$ MPa, $\nu = 0.350$, and $\sigma_Y = 60$ MPa, respectively. Since significant nonlinearity occurs with large deformation of the adhesive layer, dynamic explicit method was employed. A commercial finite element package ABAQUS/Explicit 2017 was used

Figure 7: FE model and boundary conditions under mode I loading.

Figure 8: FE model and boundary conditions in under mode II (shear) loading.

Table 1: Material properties of CFRP (T800S/#2592).

Young's moduli	E_{11} [GPa]	165.0
	$E_{22} = E_{33}$ [GPa]	7.7
Shear moduli	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ [GPa]	3.8
	G_{23} [GPa]	3.4
Poisson's ratios	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$ [-]	0.33
	ν_{23} [-]	0.45

Table 2: Material properties of epoxy adhesive (NB102).

Young's modulus	E [MPa]	3465
Poisson's ratios	ν [-]	0.366
Initial hydrostatic tension strength	p_0 [MPa]	3.3
Friction angle	β [deg.]	21.3

Table 3: Relationship between onset of damage of adhesive and stress triaxiality.

Stress triaxiality [-]	Equivalent plastic strain at the onset of damage [-]
0.0	0.4
0.333	0.1

for the analyses. The density of the adhesive part and the carrier part was 1.3 g/cm^3 , and that of the CFRP part was 1.7 g/cm^3 . Mass scaling value of 10^7 was used for the whole model in order to reduce the computational cost.

3.2 Results and discussion of finite-element analyses

Figure 9 presents damage index contour and failure morphology of the mode I model. Only the adhesive part is shown in Figure 9. Since the boundary condition of the FE models was not exactly similar to the specimen used for the experiments, qualitative evaluation was made for the models. Contrary to the experimental results, interfacial damage zone was not observed for the mode I model, i.e. the crack propagated in the center of adhesive layer. The discrepancy could be attributed to the difference in constrain of adhesive by CFRP. These results suggest that thermal stress and constrain in the z -direction have to be taken into account for microscopic damage simulation under mode I loading.

Figure 10 compares the maximum principal strain distribution obtained by mode II fracture toughness tests and FE analysis of the mode II model. The location of strain concentration and strain distribution obtained by the FE analysis well agreed with that of experimental results. Elements breakage

Figure 9 Damage index distribution and failure elements around crack tip.

(a) Experiment

(b) FE analysis

Figure 10: Comparison of maximum principal distribution obtained by the DIC method and FE analysis under mode II loading.

around the carriers were observed as well as the experimental results (Fig. 6). The failure of the adhesive occurred within the adhesive layer. These results imply that microscopic failure can be simulated by using the Drucker-Prager yielding condition and simple damage model under mode II loading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present study experimentally and numerically examines microscopic failure mechanisms in adhesively bonded CFRP joints under mode I and mode II loading. In-situ observation of fracture process in the adhesive layer was carried out with an optical microscope. High-magnification in-situ observation was achieved by using the wedge loaded DCB and DENT specimens. Strain field was quantitatively analyzed by applying the DIC method to the digital micrographs. In addition, microscopic damage analysis was carried out using the Drucker-Prager yielding condition and simple damage model. adhesive resin, CFRPs, and polyester carriers were modeled in order to simulate the microscopic damage behavior. The conclusions from the studies are summarized as follows.

- (1) Under mode I loading, interfacial damage zone first formed because strain concentration occurred along the CFRP/adhesive interface because interfacial damage zone was formed along the interface. The crack propagated along the CFRP/adhesive interface. The maximum principal strain reached approximately 30% at the onset of crack growth in the present joints.
- (2) Under mode II loading, microcracks around polyester carrier formed first, and then macroscopic crack growth occurred due to the coalescing microcracks. The microcracks formed when the maximum principal strain in adhesive layer locally reached approximately 70%. The maximum principal strain in the adhesive resin exceeded 100% at the onset of crack growth.
- (3) Failure morphology, strain distribution, and location of strain concentration were well simulated under mode II loading using the Drucker-Prager yielding condition and simple damage model. Contrary to the results under mode II loading, interfacial damage zone observed in the experiments was not able to be simulated under mode I loading by using the present method. These results suggest that thermal stress and constrain in the width direction have to be taken into account for the microscopic damage simulation under mode I loading.

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